

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL FACTORS ON VIOLENCE ACROSS VARIED INCOME ECONOMIES

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Abstract

Violence and criminal activities have long persisted as significant phenomena shaping human history. This study delves into the complex inquiry regarding the influence of social factors on violence, specifically within diverse income economies. The research scrutinizes the intricate interplay between violence and socioeconomic elements across a spectrum of income-based classifications. A noteworthy observation emerges in the behaviour of middle-income economies, deviating from established global norms. While a higher Gross Domestic Product (GDP) typically aligns with reduced violence, upper-middle income countries challenge this trend by exhibiting elevated violence despite experiencing economic growth. This intriguing pattern may be attributed to nuanced interactions between GDP and GDP per capita, leading to exacerbated inequality and the attenuation of social services. Furthermore, lower middle-income economies manifest a noteworthy departure from the expected correlation between social protection and violence, thereby suggesting intricate distribution dynamics warranting deeper exploration.

Key Words: Violence, diverse income economies, Panel Data

JEL: E000, O570, C500

1. Introduction

Violence has perpetually marred human history, casting a dark shadow from ancient civilizations to today's interconnected world (Walby and Allen, 2004). Societies have grappled with these complex issues across time, impacting individuals from all walks of life (Piquero et al., 2012). This introduction delves into the multifaceted nature of global violence, illuminating its historical context, social dynamics, and particularly, the economic factors contributing to its prevalence today.

The spectrum of violence varies widely across jurisdictions due to cultural norms, legislative approaches, and enforcement capabilities. Violence, characterized by acts of physical force intended to harm, inflicts both physical and psychological damage.

Throughout history, violence has arisen from territorial disputes, power struggles, ideological clashes, and resource competition (Jabri, 1996). The 20th century bore witness to some of the deadliest acts of violence, notably World War I and World War II, which claimed millions of lives and reshaped the global geopolitical landscape (Huntington, 2015).

India, a diverse nation with a rich history, grapples with its share of violence and crime challenges (Drèze and Khera, 2000). Communal and religious tensions, gender-based violence, political strife, and terrorism have tested the fabric of Indian society. Understanding these complexities is crucial for formulating targeted strategies to address root causes and promote peace and harmony.

No child enters the world as an inherently criminal being; it is the adversities and challenges they

encounter that compel some to resort to unjust means. This paper embarks on a systematic investigation to determine if factors such as employment assistance and social security contribute to reducing violence within a country. While previous research has explored similar concepts (Tekkas Kerman & Betrus, 2020; Grover, 2019), there is a noticeable research gap concerning income economies. Empirical evidence from recent research (Shaari et al., 2023) underscores the substantial influence of employment opportunities, robust social security systems, and unemployment assistance in shaping a nation's violence levels.

Nations offering ample employment prospects and comprehensive social safety nets typically witness reduced desperation and lower crime rates (Bisong, 2020). Adequate unemployment assistance acts as a protective buffer against economic shocks, reducing the inclination of individuals to engage in criminal activities. Moreover, a robust Gross Domestic Product (GDP) contributes to a nation's stability by fostering economic growth, which, in turn, can serve as a deterrent to violence. In essence, a thriving economy, combined with accessible employment opportunities and robust social safety nets, constitutes a formidable barrier against the origins of violence within society, ultimately promoting an environment of peace and well-being.

Nonetheless, it is essential to recognize that certain countries may present contradictory empirical evidence (Cox et al., 2019). Therefore, this study endeavours to conduct an exhaustive examination of the impact of macroeconomic shocks on violence across diverse countries over a decade,

shedding further light on the complex interplay between economic factors and societal violence.

2. Data

The empirical data concerning statistics on violence and crime across various countries spanning a decade (2012-2021) has been obtained from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI). In our study, we have employed a simplified income classification based on the World Development Indicators (WDI) data for the year 2020. This refined categorization is designed to enhance clarity and effectively distinguish countries and regions based on their income levels. The following provides the detailed definitions for each of the four main categories:

Code 0: Low-Income Economies - This category includes countries with an income level equal to or below \$1,085.

Code 1: Lower Middle-Income Economies - Encompassing countries with an income range between \$1,085 and \$4,255.

Code 2: Upper Middle-Income Economies - Comprising countries with an income range from \$4,256 to \$13,205.

Code 3: High-Income Economies - This category consists of countries with an income level exceeding \$13,205.

By adopting this refined income classification, our analysis aims to offer a more nuanced understanding of the disparities and dynamics among countries and regions based on their income levels. This differentiation is essential in discerning the potential influence of socio-economic factors and identifying patterns that may impact various aspects of these economies. Such an approach enables us to conduct a more targeted and insightful examination of the relationships

between income levels and other variables³ within the context of our study.

3. Methodology:

In our research study, we adopted a fixed effect approach to analyse the dynamics between violence, unemployment benefits, social insurance, social protection, population, and unemployment. Panel data enables us to capture both cross-sectional and time-series variations, thereby offering a robust analysis of the relationships over the 10-year period (2012-2021) and across various countries.

To assess the appropriateness of employing random effects in our panel data models, we conducted the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier Test. The objective of this test is to determine whether random effects are statistically significant and thus, whether it is appropriate to assume that the unobserved individual-specific effects are not correlated with the explanatory variables. Surprisingly, the results indicate that random effects are significant in all equations, implying that the unobserved heterogeneity across countries significantly influences the dependent variables.

However, we also sought to evaluate the relevance of fixed effects by employing the Hausman Test. This test helps us to determine whether there is a systematic difference between the individual-specific effects and the explanatory variables, which could lead to endogeneity issues. Interestingly, the Hausman Test results indicate that fixed effects are indeed relevant in all the cases, suggesting that the unobserved heterogeneity is

³ The study incorporates several key variables. For variable details see Appendix.

correlated with the explanatory variables.

Given these findings, we have decided to proceed with the fixed effects model in our analysis. The inclusion of fixed effects accounts for the individual-specific heterogeneity that may be correlated with the explanatory variables, thereby providing more reliable estimates of the relationships between violence and the socio-economic factors under consideration. The adoption of the fixed effects model in our panel data analysis allows us to control for the unobserved heterogeneity, ensuring that the estimated effects of unemployment benefits, social insurance, social protection, population, and unemployment on violence are not biased. Consequently, our study aims to shed light on the intricate interplay between socio-economic factors and violence, considering the individual characteristics of each country while accounting for the potential endogeneity concerns.

4. Results

Based on our analysis, a notable negative and statistically significant relationship has been observed between violence and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of countries. The findings reveal that as the GDP of a country increases, there is a significant reduction in the level of violence within that country. In other words, higher GDP is associated with a considerable decrease in violence incidents. The probable reason behind the negative relation can be attributed to the fact that higher GDP ensures economic stability, development, upliftment of social welfare, improved education so on. Reduced economic disparities and improved living

conditions can decrease tensions and potential triggers for violence. Education can foster awareness and empathy, leading to a more understanding and peaceful society.

Table 1: World Panel Analysis

Country Code:	All
Base Model	Fixed Effect
Dependent Variable	Violence
R-Square:	
Within	0.81
Between	0.07
Overall	0.12
GDP	-9.78** (2.98)
Unemployment Benefits	-0.61** (0.25)
Social Insurance	5.94** (1.59)
Social Protection	-8.40** (2.55)
Population	35.48** (11.98)
Unemployment	-0.51 (0.83)
Constant	-150.57** (57.71)
Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

Table 1 highlights a notable negative and statistically significant relationship between unemployment benefits and violence. When unemployment benefits are accessible and provide sufficient financial support to those without work, the incidence of violent behaviour tends to decrease. As a result, desperate acts that may lead to criminal activities, such as theft or robbery, are mitigated. This suggests that a well-functioning welfare system with adequate unemployment benefits can contribute to fostering a more peaceful and stable society.

Social insurance programs are designed to provide financial support and security to individuals during times of need, such as unemployment, retirement, disability, or healthcare emergencies. Based on our analysis, a notable positive and statistically significant relationship has been observed between violence and social insurance programs. The probable reason behind the positive relation can be attributed to the fact that poor administration and misallocation of resources within social insurance programs can create distrust and resentment among the population which may lead to social unrest and protests, which may escalate into violence.

The negative correlation between social protection and violence refers to the idea that well-designed and effectively implemented social protection programs such as food assistance healthcare support etc, help alleviate financial stress and provide a safety net for those facing economic challenges. From table 1, we observe a notable positive and statistically significant relationship between violence and population. As the population of a city or region increases, there is a larger pool of potential offenders, victims, and opportunities for criminal activity. Also, we observe a negative correlation between violence and unemployment. Unemployment often leads to a decline in income, pushing some individuals towards criminal activities as a means of survival, but there are factors that explain the negative relation between violence and unemployment. In most economies, Government provides unemployment benefits and grants to the unemployed, thus providing them

with financial security and this in return leads to decrease in violence.

Table 2: Low Income Economies

Country Code:	0
Base Model	Fixed Effect
Dependent Variable	Violence
R-Square	
Within	0.145
Between	0.025
Overall	0.0258
GDP	-0.919 (0.79)
Unemployment Benefits	Data unavailable
Social Insurance	Data unavailable
Social Protection	Data unavailable
Population	5.496*** (1.337)
Unemployment	-1.102** (0.489)
Constant	-24.945*** (7.621)
Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

Our analysis reveals an apparent yet nonsignificant inverse relation between violence and a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This trend can likely be attributed to the positive effects of a higher GDP, such as economic stability, social development, improved education, and elevated living standards, which collectively mitigate the incentives for criminal engagement.

In low-income economies experiencing rapid population growth, violence exhibits a highly significant positive relationship with population size. This connection can be rationalized by the prevalence of unemployment, poverty, and income inequality in such contexts. Limited access to quality education and resources also contributes to

heightened criminal activities among the youth.

Table 2 underscores a statistically significant negative link between violence and unemployment, implying that elevated unemployment rates correspond to reduced incidents of violence. This can potentially be attributed to government initiatives and support systems for the unemployed, fostering financial security and consequently lowering the occurrence of violent incidents.

Table 3: Lower-Middle Income Economies

Country Code:	1
Base Model	Fixed Effect
Dependent Variable	Violence
R-Square	
Within	0.0789
Between	0.5896
Overall	0.5229
GDP	-2.262 (1.427)
Unemployment Benefits	Data unavailable
Social Insurance	0.0018 (0.426)
Social Protection	0.8538* (0.5045)
Population	2.813** (1.488)
Unemployment	0.220 (0.856)
Constant	7.684 (6.413)
Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

For 74 Lower Middle-Income economies, including India, we identify an insignificant negative correlation between violence and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This suggests that augmented GDP corresponds to a substantial reduction in violence incidents, driven by enhanced economic conditions, decreased

poverty, amplified educational access, developmental strides, and effective social programs.

Table 3 underscores an insignificant positive relationship between violence and social insurance. This link can be attributed to flawed administration and resource misallocation within social insurance programs, fostering distrust and resentment that might escalate into violence. Similarly, a statistically significant positive connection exists between violence and social protection, stemming from inadequately structured programs prone to corruption and mismanagement, thereby triggering social unrest.

Furthermore, Table 3 reveals a significant positive correlation between violence and population. Factors like youth bulge, resource scarcity, and unemployment contribute to increased violence in densely populated regions. Conversely, a positive yet insignificant connection is found between violence and unemployment in lower middle-income economies. Heightened unemployment intensifies violence due to financial strain, particularly for those unable to fulfil basic needs, potentially pushing some towards criminal behaviour.

Among 71 Upper Middle-Income economies, both population size and GDP per capita exhibit significant associations with violence. Remarkably, the relationship's coefficient value is negative for population size and positive for GDP per capita, diverging from patterns observed in other economies and overall model results. Economic growth often accompanies widening income inequality, fostering social tensions that contribute to violence, especially in urban areas marked by

differing living standards. As economies advance, increased investment in education and skill development leads to higher levels of education across the population, consequently reducing criminal activities.

Table 4: Upper-Middle Income Economies

Country Code:	2
Base Model	Fixed Effect
Dependent Variable	Violence
R-Square	
Within	0.7412
Between	0.0401
Overall	0.1064
GDP	1.716* (0.965)
Unemployment Benefits	Data unavailable
Social Insurance	0.388** (0.197)
Social Protection	-1.478*** (0.182)
Population	-4.937** (2.4708)
Unemployment	-0.085 (0.1603)
Constant	24.293** (9.520)
Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

Table 4 highlights a positive link between violence and social insurance, likely stemming from inadequate administration and resource misallocation within social insurance schemes, leading to distrust, resentment, and escalating social unrest. Conversely, the negative correlation between social protection and violence implies that well-structured programs, such as food assistance and healthcare support, alleviate financial strain, offering a safety net for those grappling with economic challenges.

Furthermore, Table 4 underscores a negative relationship between violence and unemployment in upper middle-income economies. Elevated unemployment corresponds to a notable reduction in violence incidents, attributed to comprehensive poverty and unemployment alleviation programs often pursued in these economies.

High-Income economies commonly exhibit diminished poverty rates and greater income equality, factors that tend to mitigate violence drivers. Consequently, a higher Gross Domestic Product correlates with decreased violence incidents within this bracket. However, our results are insignificant.

Table 5: High Income Economies

Country Code:	3
Base Model	Fixed Effect
Dependent Variable	Violence
R-Square	
Within	0.695
Between	0.452
Overall	0.4284
GDP	-0.2065 (0.229)
Unemployment Benefits	Data unavailable
Social Insurance	Data unavailable
Social Protection	Data unavailable
Population	4.3685*** (0.465)
Unemployment	-0.0404 (0.111)
Constant	-29.175*** (2.364)
Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

Table 5 unveils a significant positive relation between violence and population size. In High-Income economies, elevated urbanization fosters larger cities and metropolitan

zones, consequently amplifying crime opportunities. As discussed earlier, a larger population size indicates reduced opportunity to exploit rivalry goods including medical benefits, educational opportunities, or employment opportunities. Therefore, the feeling of being left out inculcates the need to seek shelter under violent options.

Moreover, a negative yet insignificant link surfaces between violence and unemployment. High-Income economies boast robust social services and support mechanisms, effectively counteracting the repercussions of unemployment.

5. Discussion

It is intriguing to observe that middle-income economies exhibit distinct behaviour in contrast to other global economic categories. While higher GDP is associated with lower violence on a global scale, upper-middle income economies defy this pattern, demonstrating that nations with higher GDP also experience elevated incidences of violence. This phenomenon could stem from nuances within these economies, where higher GDP does not necessarily equate to higher GDP per capita. This disparity might amplify social or structural inequality, weaken social services, and foster intercommunity tensions. Additionally, deficient safety policies could create an environment ripe for criminal opportunities.

Similarly, lower middle-income economies diverge in their behaviour concerning social protection compared to other economic strata. While higher global levels of social protection correlate with lower violence, middle-income economies exhibit a contrary relationship. This complex dynamic

suggests that not all forms of social protection result in equal distribution, and certain measures might inadvertently contribute to a "prisoner syndrome," thereby increasing violence.

On a global scale, the correlation between higher population and increased violence appears logical. However, upper middle-income economies once again deviate from this trend. These countries might leverage improved social control mechanisms and more equitable resource distribution, while the diversity inherent in larger populations could nurture tolerance and reduce tension, promoting overall prosperity.

6. Conclusion

Our analysis establishes a significant and negative relationship between violence and a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Higher GDP corresponds to reduced violence, attributed to improved economic stability, social welfare, education, and decreased tensions. Unemployment benefits display a negative correlation with violence, as accessible benefits alleviate desperation and minimize potential criminal acts. Social insurance programs, while intended to offer financial support, show a notable positive correlation with violence due to mismanagement leading to social unrest. Conversely, well-designed social protection programs exhibit a negative relationship with violence by mitigating financial stress. Notably, violence is positively correlated with population, reflecting increased opportunities for crime. Additionally, a negative correlation between violence and unemployment prevails, largely due to government support providing financial security.

On a contrary, Middle-income economies deviate from the global norm: higher GDP typically means lower violence, but upper-middle income countries exhibit higher violence despite GDP gains. This might result from disparities between GDP and GDP per capita, intensifying inequality, weakening social services, and fostering tensions. In lower middle-income economies, social protection diverges—higher global protection correlates with less violence, but middle-income countries show a reverse trend due to unequal distribution. While population-violence correlation holds globally, upper middle-income economies differ, possibly due to improved social control and equitable resource allocation, while diverse populations bolster tolerance and prosperity.

In conclusion, this comprehensive exploration of violence and its intricate relationship with various social factors across diverse income economies provides valuable insights. The analysis underscores the multifaceted nature of this association, revealing how economic development, population dynamics, and social support systems can either amplify or mitigate violent tendencies. High-Income economies benefit from enhanced social services that counteract unemployment's potential influence on violence, while Middle-Income economies grapple with complex interactions between GDP, education, and inequality. These findings emphasize the need for tailored strategies addressing local contexts to effectively curb violence and foster safer societies, calling for collaborative efforts in policymaking and intervention implementation.

7. References

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8. Appendix

The study incorporates several key variables to examine the relationship between violence and socio-economic factors. These variables consist of:

- Violence: This variable represents the incidence of violent incidents or crimes within the analysed countries.
- Unemployment Benefits: This variable refers to the benefits or financial assistance provided to individuals who are unemployed and actively seeking employment.
- Social Insurance: This variable encompasses the social insurance programs or schemes that provide protection and financial support to individuals during times of unemployment, disability, or other contingencies.
- Social Protection: This variable includes various social protection

measures implemented by governments to safeguard vulnerable populations from economic and social risks, such as poverty, unemployment, and illness.

- Population: This variable represents the total number of individuals residing in each country under study.
- Unemployment Benefits: Unemployment compensation is paid by the state to unemployed workers who have lost their jobs due to layoffs or if the business closed. It is meant to provide a source of income for jobless workers until they can find employment.
- Unemployment: This variable denotes the proportion of the labour force that is currently unemployed and seeking employment opportunities.

By analysing these variables, the study aims to discern potential associations between violence and socio-economic factors, particularly focusing on unemployment-related measures and social protection initiatives. The log-log transformation technique has been employed to ensure comparability and address scaling issues, enabling a more comprehensive examination of the relationships between the variables in the model.